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RESEARCH ARTICLE

PERVASIVENESS OF THE BRAIN-DRAIN AND TALENT MANAGEMENT: THE ROLE OF CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT ON TALENT MANAGEMENT CONUNDRUM IN NIGERIA MANUFACTURING FIRMS

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ABSTRACT

The corporate brain drain wave in Nigeria which has hitherto prevented the talent war in the business environment has not shown any indication of relief in the present time. This study has investigated the pervasiveness of brain drain and its possible effect on talent management, analysing the mediating role on the relationship between brain drain pushed factors and talent management. This study utilised cross sectional research design to survey the 250 participants of the study among manufacturing organisations in Nigeria. The study used a probability random sampling to address the sampling strategy of the study. Using a hierarchical regression analysis, the outcome of the study demonstrated that lack of opportunity for career growth, financial insecurity, toxic work environment, inadequate remuneration, undervalued talented employees, job security and management style/organisational culture were possible issues that provoked wave of brain drain among employees in manufacturing industry in Nigeria and deter talent management for corporate managers in Nigeria. The study has indicated that toxic work environments, poor working conditions and poor remuneration have deterred the management of organisations from managing talented workforce in Nigeria's manufacturing industry. Therefore, the study concluded that the brain drain, called the *Japa* wave, has worsened the nation's manufacturing development and stability due to the shortage of professional employees in the industry.

KEYWORDS

Brain-Drain, Capacity Development, Job Security, Human Performance, Management Style/organisational Culture, Undervalued Talented Workforce, Work Environment, Nigeria Manufacturing Industry

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Introduction

Managing talent has become a major issue that most organizations across the continents are experiencing today. It has become a global challenge confronting all organizational development experts in a contemporary business environment. Acquiring the right talent is the greatest asset that any organization can thrive on the premise of a sustainable competitive edge. This is the reason why it is a core role of management and human capital development managers to ensure employees with the right set of skills and competencies are not just attracted but also retained in order to entrench organizational goals (Kwon & Jang, 2022). In the modern corporate business environment, turnover intention among employees is no longer pervasive again but rather brain-drain and migration to other nations have become insurgence among the skilled and competent workforce. Retaining a valuable and talented workforce can be influenced via performance-based pay, appropriate training, a challenging work environment, prioritizing employee satisfaction needs, career development, and offering enduring employee quality of work-life (Akinwale, Kuye & Akinwale, 2022). Presently, the management of organizations is experiencing talent management issues, and efforts to keep a competent and skilful workforce becomes a mirage. Fulfilling adequate compensation systems that will optimize a normative justification for productive work behaviour for most organisations today is becoming challenging. This speaks on the employees' quality of work-life, and apparently, results in a mass exodus of the workforce to where they could derive a better standard of living (Akinwale & George, 2022). The promotion of desired and talented employees in the contemporary business world for managers tends to take another form. This is influenced by the economic situation in the country and occasioned by world economic challenges around the globe. Organisations are finding it difficult to motivate their personnel yet they want high performance from these sets of employees. The study by Amankwah-Amoah (2018) discovered that employee well-being and career development are not the priority of business managers in the 21st century. Also, in the view of Enibe, Umeh, and Jennifer (2022), in their recent study, employees are not found in the equation of corporate managers but their concerns were majorly high performance and robust

organisational goals accomplishment. Anecdotal evidence indicated that Nigeria's manufacturing organisations' management is in a turbulent situation to duly engage, delight, and retain its workforce today. This has led a good proportion of the employees to leave the country and seek better employment opportunities outside the shore of their country. Brain drain has become endemic in the African region and snowballed into a pandemic of the global cankerworm. The inability of organisations and perhaps the government to adequately provide for workforce satisfaction pushed them outside their domain and to seek a better life in the global economy (Akinwale & Onokala, 2022). Brain drain, the art of migrating to yet another region for a sustainable quality of work-life, has been pervasive among nationals of the world. It is the movement of personnel with skills and requisite knowledge from one nation to another usually for better conditions of service, good living, and a better working environment (Docquier & Rapoport, 2021). As brain drain is seen as a global social challenge, its height of occurrence varies from one country to another (de Azevedo, 2022). While its nature seems minimal in the advanced world, it is a social malady in both developing and underdeveloped environments. Nigeria's version of brain drain is rampant today due to its government's nonchalant attitude towards social welfare for citizens and the ease of doing business for the organisations (Ogunbodede, 2020). Likewise, this is connected with the reality that factors provoking brain drain behaviour in less-developed and developing nations are adequately addressed in the advanced world. The attraction of well-maintained work environments in developed nations, in particular, is appealing for personnel assets in an underdeveloped work environment (Anees, Heidler, Cavaliere, & Nordin, 2021). Sustainable compensation systems, job security, employee well-being, and career development trajectory prevailing in their work environment are more attractive to the workforce in less-developed countries (Akinwale & Kuye, 2022). The majority of Nigeria's workforce are often faced with a myriad of problems that geared their decisions to move to other countries, including job satisfaction, career progression, pay, and enduring employment opportunity (Addeh, 2022). However, the

exit of these talents from the industry is becoming a colossal loss and challenge for employers, due to migration impulse and options available to the workforce today (Ojukwu, 2022). This is the part of the rationale that birth this study among other things which need serious attention.

Another germane justification and motivation of this study is the knowledge gap in this study area. Prior studies have investigated the trajectory of brain drain, how many, where, and why, using a systematic approach in quantitative analysis (Adovor, Czaika, Docquierd & Moullan, 2021). Enibe, Umeh, and Jennifer (2021) also examined brain drain and sustainable development goal three in Nigeria's socio-political landscape. Kamarulzaman, Ramnarayan, and Mocumbi (2022) investigated plugging the brain drain on the pathway of understanding the challenges and opportunities of educating healthcare professionals and issues involved in migration into the international market. Another recent study by Gowda, Alhazza, Cahill, Ong & Flaherty (2022) analyzed the stemming of the brain drain of medical graduates from developing nations, its controversies, and solutions. However, all the identified prior studies were suffering from a knowledge void gap as knowledge did not exist in the actual study setting and theories from their related research domains and the outcome of their study differ from what was expected. This is the gap that this present study is set to fill and the reason it is of interest to examine the pervasiveness of the brain drain trend and talent management concern, especially in the manufacturing industry which is not much dominant in the research space. Moreover, knowledge impact has not been clarified, well-studied, and reported, thus, further research is required which is the reason for this study.

Literature Review

Brain drain and talent management have been two-edged sword that seems challenging for countries of the world to manage. Human capital is one of the major strengths of any corporate organisation. In the present modern and turbulent business ecosystem, companies are struggling to keep and maintain their personnel. To improve productivity, businesses are under rigorous pressure to delight and retain their workforce. The mass exodus of skilled, committed, and competent employees portend a grave consequence for the organisation. High brain drain insurgence has been identified as one of the challenges facing a majority of industries in

Nigeria, especially the banking and manufacturing sectors (Docquier, & Iftikhar, 2019). Andersen and Rasmussen (2022) argued that economic and social-cultural issues across the world have provoked a multitude of people to seek improved futures in other countries.

A meta-analysis of research that investigates the consequence of talent management challenges on the brain drain framework offers some support for the validity of brain drain syndrome among individuals who are pressing for quality work-life trends (Meyers, van Woerkom, Paauwe & Dries, 2020). Extant brain drain literature reveals that brain drain has been a major issue confronting industries driven by knowledge personnel, especially in the African continent (Reade, McKenna & Oetzel, 2019). Nevertheless, it also influences and covers an excessively large part of the component of global brain drain syndrome. An integrative model of talent management and brain drain trajectory proposed by Metcalfe, Makarem & Afiouni (2021) reveals that organisational factors may be the major cause of migration. Abeuova and Muratbekova-Touron, (2019) argued that the high volume of qualified and trained personnel is soaring in geometrical progression in the last few years. This establishes serious instability in the economy of a country and a sharp decrease in the gross domestic product (GDP) of nations. This further shows a terrible decline in people's standard of living. The movement of qualified and talented workforce from one region to another has reduced the development of several countries (Gallardo-Gallardo, Thunnissen, & Scullion, 2022). Latukha, Shagalkina, Mitskevich, and Strogetskaaya (2021) maintained that several factors informed the decision of people to migrate to foreign countries. The major ones are deficient infrastructure and facilities, scarce resources, poor salaries, and undervalue of talented and intellectual personnel (Latukha & Veselova, 2019).

Theoretical Underpinning & Framework

Talent-Based Theory

The talent-based theory is one of the underpinning theories that resonate with this present study. The theory of talent-based view as advanced by Amabile (2001) prescribes that skill and talent is the only

resource available to achieve a sustainable edge for organisations, and as such, managers must strive to prioritise efforts at attracting and maintaining talented employees (Sparrow & Makram, 2015). The theory emphasizes that organisations should ensure that a competent and talented workforce must be preserved as the unending war for talent is perennial. Therefore, managers should adequately seek plausible means of attracting, preserving, engaging, and retaining talented personnel for possible organisational goal accomplishment. This is the rationale why Barney, Ketchen, and Wright (2021) hypothesized from the resource-based view perspective that a sustainable competitive edge is hinged on the valuable, rare, imitable resources of organisation. Therefore, talented employees are the ones who are rare, valuable, and difficult to imitate as well as scarce resources that play a vital role in enduring organisational performance. In a bid to underscore the importance of talent-based theory, Ojogiwa and Qwabe (2021) demonstrated that the role of organisations is not to establish talent but is considered a talent hub integration, given the fact that talent is embedded in employees, and organisations only coordinate and blend the crops of attracted talents, offering a structural pattern of coordination and co-operation between the talented employees (Gallardo-Gallardo *et al.*, 2020).

The talent-based perspective of the organisation provides significance to develop and improve the competency of the workforce of the organisation through an orderly and scientific procedure of amassing talent as well as talent transfer, and dissemination to obtain a sustainable competitive edge (Almomani, Sweis, & Obeidat, 2022). According to the resource-based proponent, competing organisations engage in rivalry based on the heterogeneity and immovability of their capabilities and resources (Barney *et al.*, 2021). However, resources can be tangible, human, and firm in nature, and they can be utilised to execute value-creating strategies (Spies, Schauer, Bindel & Pfeiffer, 2022). Thus, the human resources aspect of the organisation is the most valuable and movable asset available to firms which needed to be maintained and preserved for organisations to sustain competitive advantage. Such that the employees will not move away from the organisation. The talent-based theory is largely driven by the view that the right set of

individuals in the right position will place the organisation in a vantage position in the workplace environment (Wang, Xu, Zhao, & Bian, 2022). It is believed that allocating the right employee to the right position will help them to provide their optimal ability and put their talent to productive use. However, this theory is connected with one of the focuses of this study, the talent management conundrum. This shows that there is a relationship between a talent-based theory with this study concisely.

Human Capital Theory

Human capital theory is a cornerstone concept in economics and social sciences that highlights the significance of human knowledge, skills, and capabilities as valuable economic assets. This theory proposes that investing in people through education, training, and healthcare can yield economic benefits for both individuals and society at large. It conceptualizes human capital as a collection of knowledge, habits, social and personality traits, including creativity, that contribute to an individual's ability to perform labor and generate economic value ((Lin *et al.*, 2017). Proponents of this theory argue that humans can enhance their productivity and efficiency by focusing more on education and training. Human capital theory encompasses the study of human resources and examines how societal functioning contributes to economic value creation. It's important to note that in the labour market, individuals bring varying levels of education, knowledge, skills, and abilities, along with their expectations, to the workplace (Dirani, & Nafukho, 2018). Research suggests that a person with more education and better training can provide a greater amount of useful productive effort compared to someone with less education and training (Sohel-Uz-Zaman *et al.*, 2022; Callaghan, 2018). The value of human capital theory is widely recognized for its potential to improve organizational performance. Consequently, organizations rely on their employees' skills, knowledge, and abilities as key drivers of value creation.

The concept of human capital has its roots in the eighteenth century when Adam Smith recognized the importance of human capability in production. However, the term "human capital" was formally introduced by Schultz in 1961 in the American Economic Review. The

concept gained widespread recognition after Gary Becker, who pioneered "human capital theory," won the Nobel Prize. Becker posited that varying levels of education and training result in different wage and salary levels, suggesting that increased knowledge, skills, and abilities lead to better job prospects. Becker viewed human capital as a physical means of production, emphasizing that organizations invest in human capital through education, training, and health initiatives. Building on this, Wuttaphan (2017) expanded the components of human capital to include abilities, knowledge, skills, personal talent, behaviour, and effort. He further detailed these components; (i). Knowledge which encompasses IQ, intelligence, and both general and specific work-related knowledge. (ii). Skills which refer to work-related expertise, including physical and procedural aspects of job performance. (iii). Talent describes the innate personal characteristics that can be enhanced through development. (iv). Behavior patterns are the observable actions, norms, ethics, and personal beliefs. (v). Effort describes the application of one's resources (talent, experience, knowledge, and ability) towards successful work outcomes. (vi). Time emphasizes an additional factor in human capital development.

Marginson (2019) noted that human capital can be accumulated through various means, including education, training, migration, and health improvements. Firms invest in human capital, viewing employees as assets and expecting future returns on their investment. Similarly, individuals invest in education or training, anticipating that acquired knowledge and skills will enhance their career prospects. The theory emphasizes that employers should focus on improving their workforce to achieve business success. Holden & Biddle (2017) argue that this focus on workforce development is central to human capital theory. Investments in human capital are believed to benefit employees individually while also advancing corporate objectives, output, and revenue. Recent perspectives, such as those of Huo (2024), suggest that organizations have a duty of care towards their employees, including supporting career progression and well-being. Aslam *et al.* (2024) caution that poor employee relations can lead to feelings of being undervalued and unmotivated, potentially impacting productivity and retention. This theory aligns with the

study's focus on talent management, emphasizing the importance of nurturing and developing employees' capabilities for mutual benefit.

Conceptual Review and Hypotheses Development Lack of Career Progression and Talent Management Conundrum

Professional growth, otherwise termed lack of career progression always hinders employees from remaining with the organisation for a very long time. This often time deters an organisation's capability to manage talent appropriately to their advantage. The concept of talent management holds significant appeal for various reasons. It addresses the growing recognition among managers and HR professionals that they should be more proactive in developing their organization's workforce for future needs. Talent management is often viewed as the primary vehicle for achieving this goal. Furthermore, talent management can encompass career development strategies, an area that has been challenging for organizations to navigate in recent years. This challenge arose as the responsibility for career progression has increasingly shifted to individual employees. Understanding the psychological contracts between an organization and its employees is crucial for implementing effective talent management processes (Okunade & Bakere, 2020). These contracts involve the implicit expectations and obligations between employers and employees, including career trajectories and the value employees bring to the organization. Professional cultures present a unique challenge in talent management. In these environments, employees often feel a stronger allegiance to their profession rather than to a specific organization. This dynamic can complicate talent retention and development strategies. Effective talent management requires a nuanced approach that balances organizational needs with individual career aspirations. It involves creating an environment that fosters professional growth while also aligning with the organization's strategic objectives. By doing so, organizations can better attract, develop, and retain key talent, ultimately enhancing their competitive position in the market.

Many organizations are wary of investing heavily in developing high-potential employees, fearing the risk of losing their investment. This concern stems from the shift in the employer-employee relationship that occurred in the 1990s. The traditional "psychological contract" based on loyalty and long-term service has given way to a new paradigm emphasizing self-directed careers and the pursuit of better opportunities (Aljbour, Ali & French, 2024). Despite this shift, research shows that employees still desire positive work environments that foster career growth. Mitosis *et al.* (2021) found that implementing talent management strategies within a supportive and healthy workplace can significantly enhance employee retention. Rasheed *et al.* (2020) corroborated this, noting that employees are more likely to remain with their current employers when they perceive ample career opportunities and maintain job satisfaction. Kähkönen *et al.* (2021) highlighted the negative impact of perceived inadequate career progression on employee satisfaction. Building on this, Ashraf (2019) observed that employees tend to favour companies with a culture that prioritizes career development. When employees sense limited growth prospects, they are more inclined to seek opportunities elsewhere. Consequently, the absence of robust career progression opportunities, particularly in corporate cultures that don't prioritize such development, poses a significant challenge for organizational talent management (Aljbour, Ali & French, 2023). This misalignment between employee expectations and organizational practices can lead to increased turnover and difficulties in retaining top talent. Effective talent management strategies, therefore, need to balance the organization's need for stability with employees' desires for growth and advancement. This may involve creating clear career pathways, offering regular skill development opportunities, and fostering a culture that values and rewards employee growth and contribution.

Financial Insecurity and Talent Management Conundrum

The exodus of skilled professionals, commonly known as brain drain, creates dual impacts, it depletes the workforce in source nations while enhancing innovation capabilities in destination countries. This phenomenon has prompted serious concerns among numerous nations about its potentially devastating effects on their technical knowledge

base. The development and progress of any nation fundamentally depend on its skilled citizenry to architect and build its future. Similarly, organizations rely heavily on exceptional employees and competent leadership for their success. This interconnected relationship between talent and development becomes starkly evident when examining the consequences of brain drain. It is in this line of thought that some studies established the reason for this paradigm change in talent management issues in the corporate work environment (Rydzik & Bal, 2024; Munawar, 2024). A recent study by Akinwale, Akinwale and Kuye (2024) demonstrated that financial security provoked several employees in Nigeria to migrate to yet another nation. It has been argued that the workforce is attributing financial insecurity and poor pay from the workplace as major challenges to managing talent in Nigeria's corporate work environment (Tambunan, Tanuwijaya, & Gunawan, 2024). Today, employees cite financial insecurity, coupled with the challenging economic issues in various national economies, as one of the core problems of retaining the best talent in organisations (Ni, Wu, Zhen, & Wu, 2024).

Ho1: Lack of career progression, and financial Insecurity are not determinants of brain drain and talent management conundrum

Work Environment and Talent Management Conundrum

Since researchers introduced the concept of the *war for talent* and recognized high-performing individuals as crucial drivers of organizational success, workplace talent management has become an increasingly important focus in business literature (Akinwale & George, 2020). A favourable and positive work environment is crucial to retaining talent in corporate organisations. Managers across all organisations recognise the essence of retaining top talent but the work environment and condition of work make this retention more challenging oftentimes (Mattarelli, Cochis, Bertolotti, & Ungureanu, 2024). However, the workplace environment significantly influences employee performance and talent management outcomes in both positive and negative ways. With people using approximately half of their lives at the workplace, the organizational setting substantially

impacts their mental wellbeing, behaviours, capabilities, and professional development. While international organizations advocate for workers' rights, research suggests that an enhanced workplace environment correlates with improved productivity, better talent retention, and stronger organizational outcomes. Specifically, the physical office space can motivate employees and enhance their performance, ultimately contributing to more effective talent management practices. It is crucial to understand that work environment is significant to promoting talented employees (Dullah, Limigiani, & Suwardi, 2023)

Inadequate Pay and Talent Management Conundrum

The intersection of compensation and talent management presents one of the most pressing challenges in modern organizational dynamics. At its core, this conundrum stems from the delicate balance between an organization's financial constraints and its need to attract, retain, and motivate high-performing talent (Thakre, 2024). Organisations often find themselves caught in a vicious cycle where inadequate pay leads to employee dissatisfaction, reduced productivity, and ultimately, talent drain (Akinwale, & Goerge, 2023). This creates a ripple effect throughout the organization, as the cost of recruiting and training new employees often exceeds the investment required to maintain competitive compensation for existing staff.

The complexity of this issue is further amplified by the evolving nature of work and worker expectations. Today's workforce, particularly millennials and Gen Z employees, seeks more than just monetary compensation; they demand comprehensive benefits packages, work-life balance, career growth opportunities, and meaningful work. However, when base compensation fails to meet market standards or living wage requirements, these additional benefits lose their appeal (Siwendu & Ambe, 2024). Organizations must recognize that inadequate pay can undermine even the most well-designed talent management strategies, as financial security remains a fundamental human need. The talent management conundrum becomes particularly acute in industries experiencing rapid growth or transformation. Companies may find themselves competing for skilled professionals against better-funded competitors, while simultaneously struggling to maintain payroll costs within sustainable levels. This creates a paradoxical situation where

organizations need top talent to drive innovation and growth but lack the financial resources to attract and retain such talent. Trisnowati, Asropi and Sutrisno, (2024) were of the view that organizations must now benchmark their compensation packages against global standards while considering local market conditions and cost of living variations. This global dimension has made the relationship between pay and talent management more intricate than ever before, requiring organizations to develop more sophisticated and nuanced approaches to both compensation and talent development strategies. Organizations that fail to resolve this conundrum risk falling into a downward spiral of decreased productivity, higher turnover, and diminished competitive advantage in an increasingly knowledge-based economy.

Ho2: Lack of career progression, financial Insecurity, toxic work environment and inadequate pay are not determinants of brain drain and talent management conundrum

Undervalued Talented Workforce and Talent Management Conundrum

The extant literature identifies a significant disconnect between how organizations value their talented workforce and effective talent management practices (Tran & Kelley, 2024). While organizations acknowledge the importance of talent management, studies show they often fail to properly assess, compensate, and develop their skilled employees (Williams, 2024). This "talent management paradox" manifests in inadequate compensation, limited recognition, and restricted career growth opportunities. Recent studies indicate that only a small percentage of organizations successfully implement effective talent valuation systems, despite claiming talent management as a priority. This misalignment leads to higher turnover, lower engagement, and reduced organizational performance (Refuncion, 2024). In today's rapidly evolving business environment, characterized by technological advancement and changing workforce dynamics, organizations need to develop more sophisticated talent valuation approaches to maintain their competitive edge.

Job Security and Safety and Talent Management Conundrum

In today's dynamic business environment, the interconnection between job security, workplace safety,

and effective talent management presents a significant organizational challenge. Research indicates that employees' perception of job security and workplace safety fundamentally influences their engagement, productivity, and long-term commitment to organizations (Gupta, Chakravoty, Garg & Singh, 2024). Studies by Maslow (1943) and subsequent researchers consistently identify security as a fundamental human need, directly impacting talent retention and organizational performance (Shahid, Tufail, Shahid, & Ismail, 2021). Recent global events, particularly the COVID-19 pandemic, have dramatically heightened awareness of workplace safety concerns and job security issues, forcing organizations to reconceptualize their talent management strategies. Contemporary literature emphasizes the evolving nature of job security in the context of rapid technological advancement and economic volatility. Organizations face the complex task of balancing workforce stability with organizational agility, often leading to what scholars term the "security-flexibility paradox." This challenge is compounded by the increasing prevalence of automation, artificial intelligence, and digital transformation, which create uncertainty about future job roles and required skills (Gupta & Dhal, 2024). The safety dimension of talent management extends beyond physical workplace safety to encompass psychological safety and well-being. Studies indicate that organizations fostering environments where employees feel secure in expressing ideas, taking calculated risks, and contributing to innovation demonstrate higher success rates in talent retention and development.

H03: Lack of career progression, financial Insecurity, toxic work environment, inadequate pay, undervalued talented workforce, and job security/safety are not determinants of brain drain and talent management conundrum

Management Style/Organisational Culture and Talent Management Conundrum

The intricate relationship between management style, organizational culture, and talent management represents a critical area of concern in contemporary organizational behavior research. Studies consistently demonstrate that leadership approaches and cultural dynamics significantly influence an organization's ability to attract, develop, and retain top talent. Research by Schein (2017) emphasizes that organizational culture, shaped primarily by management

style, acts as a powerful force in determining employee engagement, satisfaction, and long-term commitment. The literature reveals a clear correlation between inclusive, adaptive management styles and successful talent management outcomes while highlighting how rigid, authoritarian approaches often lead to talent drain and reduced organizational effectiveness (Akanji *et al.*, 2020). Contemporary research underscores the evolving expectations of the modern workforce regarding management practices and cultural environment. Studies indicate that organizations struggling with traditional, hierarchical management styles face significant challenges in talent retention, particularly among younger generations who prioritize collaborative, purpose-driven work environments. The "culture-talent fit" paradigm, as explored by scholars like (Udin, 2024), suggests that misalignment between management style, organizational culture, and employee values creates a fundamental obstacle to effective talent management. This misalignment often manifests in reduced employee engagement, increased turnover, and difficulty in attracting high-potential candidates.

H4: Lack of career progression, financial Insecurity, toxic work environment, inadequate pay, undervalued talented workforce, job security/safety, and management style/organisational culture are not determinants of brain drain and talent management conundrum

Capacity Development and Talent Management Conundrum

The intersection of capacity development and talent management presents a complex challenge in contemporary organizational development literature. Research indicates that organizations face increasing pressure to develop employee capabilities while simultaneously managing talent effectively in a rapidly evolving business landscape. Studies by Dai *et al.*, (2024) demonstrate that successful capacity development is intrinsically linked to organizational performance and competitive advantage, yet many organizations struggle to implement effective development programs that align with their talent management strategies. The literature emphasizes that this challenge is particularly acute in environments where technological advancement and

market dynamics require continuous skill enhancement and capability building (Mukyala & Namono, 2024). Recent research highlights the evolving nature of capacity development in the context of modern talent management. Organizations must navigate what scholars term the "development-retention paradox," where investments in employee capacity building may inadvertently increase their marketability and flight risk. Studies by Ranadewa, and Siriwardena, (2021) indicate that while robust capacity development programs are essential for attracting and engaging top talent, organizations often struggle to create sustainable returns on these investments through improved retention and performance. The research reveals that successful organizations address this challenge by implementing integrated approaches that combine skill development with clear career progression pathways and meaningful engagement opportunities.

H5: Capacity development does not mediate the relationship between factors of brain drain and talent management conundrum

Research Methods

Research Design

The researchers utilised a descriptive approach with a cross-sectional methodology to survey employees from the manufacturing industry affected by the pervasiveness of brain drain. This cross-sectional approach was selected because it allows data collection at one specific time point, helping to minimise selection bias and ensure the sample properly represents the diverse characteristics of the entire target population (Fatimah & Singh, 2024)

Study Population and Sample Size

The study considers manufacturing firms in Lagos as the unit of analysis for the research, taking five manufacturing organisations as the study population (C-way Foods Beverages, Rite Foods Limited, Sunai Foods, Arla Foods, Viju Industries Nigeria Limited) The rationale for taking five of the manufacturing firms is that they are multi-national firms and have a large pool of employees in Lagos State yet, they are perceived to have possible signs of talent management retention in their various organisations. The total population value figure of the five organisations stands at 5000 employees. The sample size determination strategy for this study is chosen from Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) sample size

for a finite population. The sample size as derived following the suggestion from the formula of Krejcie and Morgan (1970) was 250 sample size.

Sample Strategy

This research employed probability random sampling as its methodology. This approach was selected because it ensures a balanced representation of physicians who have migrated to four different countries worldwide. This sampling method helps eliminate potential bias since every physician in the target population has an equal chance of being chosen through the random selection process (Hazari, 2024). As a result, the findings derived from these simple random samples can be considered both unbiased and applicable to the broader population.

Data Analysis Strategy

This study uses a multivariate hierarchical regression model to evaluate the pervasive factors responsible for brain drain and talent management challenges. The analysis incorporates the Macro Hayes process to examine how capacity development mediates between factors of brain drain factors and talent management challenges. The hierarchical regression method was chosen because it enables the examination of how individual predictors contribute beyond previously studied factors, serves as a statistical control measure, and helps analyze incremental validity (Paul, 2024) This approach is particularly valuable as it effectively identifies the key significant predictors of brain drain. Furthermore, it allows for meaningful model comparisons and helps identify the most suitable predictive model for specific situations (Khan, *et al.*, 2024). The Macro Hayes process was specifically selected to examine mediating relationships between the study's key constructs, as it effectively demonstrates the extended connections between various variables and factors (Agrawal & Pradhan, 2024).

Result and Discussion

Participants Demographic Profile

The participants' demographic profile shows that the employees to quit has 150 (60%) of them are male and 100 (40%) of them are female. The age range of the participants illustrates that 50 (20%) are below 40 years of age, 75 (30%) are within the age range of 45 years or above, and 70 (28%) are within the age of 45 and 50

years of age. While 55 (22%) of the participants fall within the age category of 50 years and above. The profile of the respondents shows educational background, and departments/units. The income analysis of the participants indicates that 145 (58%) are on the salary scale of 1 million naira to 1.5 million naira, 45 (18%) of the respondents are earning 2 million naira annually which made it challenging to survive the work ecosystem. 60 (24%) respondents are on a salary scale of 2.5 million naira per annum.

Analysis of Data and Test of Hypotheses

Table 2: Summary of Hierarchical Regression Analysis

Predictor	R	R ²	R ² -Chang	B	beta	t	P	Sig
Model 1	0.557	0.656	0.518				0.01	
Lack of Career Progression					0.425	0.545	5.25	0.01
Financial Insecurity					0.405	0.585	9.45	0.03
Model 2	0.611	0.658	0.473					0.01
Lack of Career Progression					0.475	0.570	8.50	0.03
Financial Insecurity					0.555	0.578	7.12	0.02
Toxic Work Environment				0.614	0.698	9.15	0.01	
Inadequate pay				0.699	0.755	11.10	0.03	

Model 3	0.649	0.692	0.41					0.03		
Lack of Career Progression							0.375	0.673	4.46	0.02
Financial Insecurity							0.410	0.628	9.33	0.03
Toxic Work Environment						0.601	0.729	10.01	0.03	
Inadequate pay						0.650	0.765	5.25	0.02	
Undervalued Talented Workforce						0.395	0.411	5.10	0.01	
Job Security/Safety							0.550	0.648	6.42	0.01
Model 4	0.595	0.702	0.485							0.01
Lack of Career Progression							0.456	0.763	7.40	0.04
Financial Insecurity							0.328	0.688	9.25	0.03
Toxic Work Environment						0.521	0.789	9.47	0.03	
Inadequate pay						0.645	0.763	5.78	0.02	
Undervalued Talented Workforce						0.574	0.530	7.15	0.01	

Job Security/Safety					0.574	0.821	6.29	0.01
Management Style/Organisational					0.574	0.821	8.14	0.01

Source: Authors' Creation from Field Survey, 2024; N= 250, P < 0.05

Table 2 demonstrates the result output regression analysis in its order of hierarchy. The research used a four-step analysis of four hierarchical processes, conducted at a four-model level. This shows a model summary of multiple hierarchical regression analysis determinants of pervasive brain drain trends within Nigerian manufacturing organisations and talent management challenges. Four-stage hierarchical multiple regression analyses were established to demonstrate the relationship between factors responsible for brain drain and talent management conundrum in Nigeria's manufacturing industry. The first model analysis involves two factors (lack of career progression, and financial security) as major determinants of brain drain among the employees of the manufacturing industry in Nigeria (R = 0.557, R² = 0.656, F₂ = 249, P < 0.01). This indicates a high level of relationship between lack of career progression, financial security and talent management conundrum at 55.7%, and R² illustrates a variance of 65.6% occurrence as the determinant of brain drain was a result of lack of career progression and financial security. This also shows a significant model at P < 0.05 which is P = 0.01. The model/stage one of the analysis depicts that lack of career progression and financial insecurity emerged as a significant element responsible for brain drain issues and talent management conundrums among the employees in the manufacturing industry. This fulfilled the first hypothesis of this study as populated that Lack of career progression, and financial security are determinants of brain drain and talent management conundrum.

The second stage/step of this model results added toxic work environment and inadequate pay as part of the predictors of brain drain which made it challenging to manage talented employees, accounting for 65.8% variations in toxic work environment and inadequate pay along the first stage significant variables in the model one (F₃, 240) = 17.75, P <

0.01. The R = 61.1% interaction among the established variables (lack of career progression, financial security, toxic work environment, inadequate pay). This indicates a high level of interactions occurring among these variables. This implies that a toxic work environment and inadequate pay have (β = 69.8%, P < and β = 75.5%) high relationships respectively. It then means that the two have a highly significant relationship with the hierarchical order in the second model, as inadequate pay is the number one factor responsible for brain drain and talent management conundrum. Therefore, the second model also is significant, predicting brain drain and accounting for talent management conundrum. Hence, the hypothesis is then rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted that lack of career progression, financial security, toxic work environment and inadequate pay are not determinants of brain drain and talent management conundrum.

The third stage of the model includes the addition of undervalued talented employees, and job security/safety. The overall model persistently predicts the brain drain issues significantly (R = 0.649, R² = 0.692, P < 0.03). This shows a combined relationship that exists at 64.9% between lack of career progression, financial security, toxic work environment, inadequate pay, undervalued talented employees, and job security. R² = 69.2% indicating variability that occurs in the brain drain as explained by the combined six determinants of brain drain, at a significant value P = 0.03. However, lack of career progression maintained its robust predictive value (β = 0.673, P < 0.02), and financial insecurity (β = 0.628, P < 0.03), Job Insecurity also continued taking its predictive stand (β = 0.648, P < 0.01), undervalued talented employees was the lowest predictor in the third model (β = 0.411, P < 0.01), toxic work environment indicated that it has a high degree of determining brain drain and talent management issue ((β = 0.729, P < 0.03), and inadequate pay also maintained its high level of prediction (β = 0.765, P < 0.02). The inclusion of the undervalued talented employees and job security/safety established a positive significant relationship with the brain drain trend among employees in manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The results demonstrated that toxic work environments and

inadequate pay remained the two dominant determinants of brain drain and talent management conundrum in the third model. This depicts that the alternate hypothesis is accepted that lack of career progression, financial insecurity, toxic work environment, inadequate pay, undervalued talented workforce, and job security/safety are determinants of brain drain and talent management conundrum.

The fourth stage of the model, the last model involves the inclusion of management style/ organisational culture. The final model consistently predicts brain drain trends and continues to account for the talent management conundrum significantly ((R= 0.595, R² = 0.702, F (5, 243) = 21.55, P < 0.01). This indicates that 59.5% of combined relationships exist between lack of career progression, financial security, toxic work environment, inadequate pay, undervalued employees, job insecurity, and management style/organisational culture and talent management conundrum. R² = 70.2% shows variations that are established in the talent management conundrum are explained by the combination of the six variables that determined brain drain and the talent management conundrum and a significant value at P = 0.01. However, management style/organisational culture and job security are dominant determinant factors in the talent management conundrum at (β = 81.1%, P = 0.01) respectively. Toxic work environment, inadequate pay, and lack of career progression continue to maintain their robust relationship in the order of the hierarchy (β = 78.9%, P = 0.03; β = 76.3%, P = 0.02; β = 76.3%, P = 0.04) respectively. On the fourth model management style/organisational culture with job insecurity/safety were the predominant factors that highly predicted talent management conundrum among manufacturing organisations. Thus, an alternate hypothesis is rather accepted that lack of career progression, financial security, toxic work environment, inadequate pay, undervalued talented workforce, job security/safety, and management style/organisational culture are determinants of brain drain and talent management conundrum.

Hos: Capacity development does not mediate the relationship between factors of brain drain and talent management conundrum

Table 3: Mediating Role of Capacity Development on the Relationship between Factors of Brain Drain and Talent Management Conundrum

Type of Effect	Variable	Effect	SE	P	LLCI	ULCI
Direct	FBD → TMC	0.0745	0.073	0.06	0.2556	0.7124
Indirect	FBD → CD → TMC	0.6557	0.054	0.001	0.0420	0.0435
Total	FBD → CD → TMC	0.7302	0.127	0.002	0.4345	0.6559

Source: Authors' Creation from Field Survey, 2024;

Note (s): CD = Capacity Development; FBD = factors Brain Drain; TMC = Talent Management Conundrum; LLCI = Lower Limit Confidence Interval; ULCI = Upper Limit Confidence Interval

Demonstrating the mediating impact of capacity development on the relationship between factors responsible for brain drain and talent management conundrum, with the aid of this MACRO PROCESS model 4 in SPSS to analyse the mediating impact of capacity development on the interactions with the research variables. Table 3 illustrates that employee capacity development full a significant mediating impact on the relationship between factors responsible for brain drain and the talent management conundrum. The result demonstrates that employee capacity development has (β = 0.0745, P < 0.06) direct effect relationship, and (β = 0.6557, P < 0.001) indirect relationship, and a total effect (β = 0.7302, P < 0.002) between factors responsive for the pervasiveness of brain drain and talent management conundrum. The result shows that there is no direct significant relationship between factors of brain drain and talent management conundrum while there exists an indirect significant relationship between factors of brain drain and talent management conundrum. This established a full mediating impact of capacity development on the relationship between factors of brain drain and talent management conundrum. Thus, this study established that capacity development fully mediates the relationship between factors of brain drain and talent management conundrum among employees of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Discussion

This study demonstrated that lack of career progression and financial insecurity have been a source of concern

discouraging employees in Nigerian manufacturing organisations from migrating to yet another better nation. Also, the same factors have made it challenging for these organisations to manage talents accordingly. The outcome of this study has shown that the inability to realise career growth by employees from manufacturing firms and financial insecurity financially have pushed the majority of the employees to better countries where they will achieve career growth and advancement in their professional life domain. The study established that there is poor career growth and progression among the employees of Nigerian manufacturing firms. However, this study takes an asymmetric position to the study of Akinwale, Kuye, and George (2024) whose recent research indicated that financial challenges and poor career growth opportunities provoked Nigerian medical professionals to foreign nations in search of quality worklife. The second hypothesis of this study established that collectively poor career growth, financial insecurity, toxic work environment, and inadequate pay provoked brain drain challenges among the employees of Nigerian manufacturing organisations. The implication is that there are plethoral factors responsible for the migration of Nigerian manufacturing employees, and unfavourable and negative work environments alongside poor salaries have also notably contributed to this menace. The outcome of this result illustrates that not only poor career growth and financial insecurity caused organised migration of employees in Nigeria manufacturing organisations but also a toxic work environment in which often time employees feel gaslighted, and no support for employee growth, low employee morale, and a perception of employee marginalised in the workplace. Poor pay is part of a toxic work environment, employees experience poor salaries which birthed financial insecurity. The outcome of this study, however, takes a similar position to the survey of Shahid *et al.*, (2024) whose discovery highlighted that poor wages and salary coupled with poor working conditions were key aspects that sent away personnel in banks to other global nations.

The third hypothesis of this study indicated that inadequate pay toxic work environment, and poor career growth took the dominant stage in determining the brain drain wave among employees in manufacturing organisations. The outcome of this result showed that Nigeria manufacturing organisations

were finding it difficult to manage talents consequent upon poor wages and salary, toxic workplaces, poor working conditions and job insecurity and incidence of poor career growth opportunities. The research revealed that Nigerian employees in manufacturing industries were not comfortable with poor recognition from the management of their organisations, financial insecurity and social insecurity in the workplace. The study outcome revealed that professional employees in manufacturing were unable to cope with lingering insecurity in the workplace and declining financial security alongside a highly toxic work ecosystem. The outcome of this study finds an asymmetrical position with the study of Okunade and Awosusi (2023) whose discovery indicated that career projection, growth, lingering financial instability and declining economic situation pushed a vast amount of Nigerian professionals to the United Kingdom to better their other life domain.

The final stage and the hierarchical model of this study established that management style and organisational culture as well as job insecurity took a predominant centre stage on the list of factors preventing the employees from staying in Nigerian manufacturing firms, and possible challenges of talent management. Toxic work environment, inadequate wages and salary lack of opportunity/support for career growth were among the major elements precluding manufacturing organisations from retaining talents in this industry. It was discovered that these germane factors have posed a terrible danger for both organisations and employees alike in Nigeria's corporate ecosystem. The study has demonstrated that there are several issues (poor opportunity for career growth, financial insecurity, toxic work environment, inadequate pay, undervalued talented employees, job insecurity, and management style/organisational culture) that professional employees in this sector battling with which made it impossible for them to remain commitment to the Nigeria organisations. They are largely contending with insignificant and poor competitive salaries compared to other relevant colleagues in the diaspora. Because of this prevailing reality, it will be challenging for employees not to quit working in Nigeria's manufacturing industry where they

will be greatly rewarded and cared for concerning fair compensation package, healthy work environment, positive organisational culture and better management style, and opportunity for career advancement among others. The outcome of this study maintains a similar position with the survey of Tran and Kelly (2024) whose discovery shows that the neo-liberal structure of foreign nations has been a source of key pulled factor tendency attracting Nigeria's professional employees, as well as financialisation tendency.

The study also indicates that employee capacity development cannot be toiled within any forward-looking organisations. Employees appreciate this concept of paradigm shift. The outcome of the study shows that capacity development will cushion the negative impact of factors of brain drain and stimulate talent management in the corporate industry. The outcome of this study finds a similar stance to the study of Ranadewa and Siriwardena (2021) whose survey demonstrated that capacity development is the game changer for all employees to achieve their career growth objective.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This present study has shown a direction that employees in Nigerian manufacturing organisations are grappling with so many challenges that have pushed them out of Nigeria in search of better offers in international countries. The study has demonstrated that a multitude of professional workforce in manufacturing firms in Nigeria have been reported to engage in mass exodus to global countries while looking for advanced means of livelihood. The study has indicated that toxic work environments, poor working conditions and poor remuneration have deterred the management of organisations from managing talented workforce in Nigeria's manufacturing industry. Therefore, the study concluded that the brain drain, called the *Japa* wave, has worsened the nation's manufacturing development and stability due to the shortage of professional employees in the industry.

Recommendations

In light of the outcome of this study, the following recommendations are palpable as a veritable intervention to offer possible solutions to the *Japa* syndrome pandemic in Nigeria's manufacturing industry:

- I. Management of organisations should ensure a positive organisational culture that will promote a positive talent management approach.

- II. Organisations should promote and encourage positive leadership and management style that will support managing talent in the industry
- III. Organisations must always make the corporate work environment healthy and favourable for the workforce. The provision of a conducive work environment and a non-toxic work ecosystem are possible solutions to prevent brain drain waves in Nigerian manufacturing firms.
- IV. Management of Nigerian manufacturing firms should ensure that the support of employee career progress and growth at all times.
- V. Organisations should ensure a culture of promoting capacity development of the personnel from time to time. This will stimulate enduring talent management and discourage the brain drain wave in Nigeria.

Theoretical Implication

The study has offered a pathway on the trajectory of brain drain and talent management issues by lending credence to the theory of human capital and talent-based view theory. The theories have shown a theoretical inclination that capacity development resonates human capital theory as a cornerstone for building the capacity of employees, investing in personnel education, training and development which will yield positive gains for both employees and management of the organisations. In the same direction, the talent-based theory has indicated that managers must prioritise efforts at attracting and maintaining talented personnel which will preserve an unending war for talent. Theoretically, this study has shown a path that organisations should adequately seek plausible means of attracting, preserving, engaging, and retaining talented personnel for possible organisational goal accomplishment.

Implication for Practice

The study has established meaningful indications concerning the causes of professional employees' brain drain wave in the Nigerian manufacturing industry. This implies in practice that the brain drain pandemic must be decisively dealt with to promote talent management of Nigerian professionals across all industries. A dearth of professional employees provokes a colossal waste of

significant human capital resources in the country. This by extension depicts a loss of competent workforce and technical manpower in Nigeria's manufacturing industry while promoting the economy of other international countries.

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